

Supplemental Materials – Scoping Review Protocol

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Appendix 1

Table 2: Conceptual Search Matrix - Preliminary Key Articles

A	A. t.	J. t.	R	ACI	M	A. E.	V. d.
(Tambe et al., 2019)	Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources Management: Challenges and a Path Forward	California Management Review	B	96	The article is based on qualitative-empirical research involving workshops and surveys. It develops a rationale for the application of AI in Human resource management (HRM).	Examination of applicants and employees. Theoretical foundation for semantic matching and fairness considerations. Rationale for the screening stage.	02/11/26 - 2:52pm
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	Artificial intelligence and digital data in recruitment. Exploring business and engineering candidates 'perceptions of organizational attractiveness	European Management Journal	B	5	Vignette based survey experiment / Experimental manipulation, N=265.	Provides data on the perceptions of generational cohorts entering the labor market. Examines technology acceptance and the evaluation of AI-driven decisions.	02/11/26 - 3:14 pm
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	Discriminated by an algorithm: a systematic review of discrimination and fairness by algorithmic decision-making in the context of HR recruitment and HR development	Business Research	B	360	Systematic Literature analysis / PRISMA guidelines / Article examined from 2014 to 2020.	Reports on fairness perceptions and the imperative to investigate them. Focuses on the CV screening process and algorithmic bias.	02/11/26 - 3:36 pm
(Köchling et al., 2021)	Highly Accurate, But Still Discriminatory	Business & Information Systems Engineering	B	73	Exploratory approach to criteria evaluation. Objective of the technical audit of algorithms with respect to their fairness.	While fairness is evaluated from a technical perspective, generational cohort-specific perceptions are not. Measuring algorithmic discrimination despite high accuracy, as well as assessing equal opportunity.	02/15/26 - 9:16 am
(Langer et al., 2019)	Highly automated job interviews: Acceptance	International Journal of Selection and Assessment	B	133	2x2 Between-Subjects-Design / N=123.	Identification of younger target groups regarding acceptance and the decline in	02/15/26 - 9:22 am

	under the influence of stakes					acceptance at high levels of automation.	
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	Ethics of AI-Enabled Recruiting and Selection: A Review and Research Agenda	Journal of Business Ethics	B	324	Systematic literature analysis employing an interpretive approach.	Examination of applicants and AI mechanisms. Classification of AI across the recruitment stages.	02/15/26 - 9:26 am
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	The duality of algorithmic management: Toward a research agenda on HRM algorithms, autonomy and value creation	Human Resource Management Review	A	162	Conceptual study grounded in structuration theory and the duality of technology framework.	Conceptual examination of employees. Abroad HRM framework with reference to CV screening and a theoretical foundation for algorithmic systems.	02/15/26 - 9:30 am
(Köchling et al., 2023)	Can I show my skills? Affective responses to artificial intelligence in the recruitment process	Review of Managerial Science	B	92	Scenario-based experiment using a Between-Subjects-Design / N=160.	It becomes evident that the generational cohort perspective remains largely unexplored. This study provides evidence on how the use of AI influences trust and fairness perceptions.	02/15/26 - 9:38 am

Legend: A – Author / A. t. – Article title / J. t. – Journal title / R – Rating (VHB-Rating 2024) / ACI – Article Citation Index / M – Methodology / A. E. – Article Evaluation / V. d. – Viewing date

Table 3: PCC-Fit - Preliminary Key Articles

Preliminary Key Articles	P (Generational Cohort)	C (Perception/TAM)	C (Recruiting)
(Tambe et al., 2019)	indirect (Examines applicants and employees)	yes	yes
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	indirect (Examines students and early-career professionals)	yes	yes
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	indirect (Examines groups of Race, Gender, Age)	yes	yes
(Köchling et al., 2021)	indirect (Examines the evaluation of fairness metrics for applicants)	yes	yes
(Langer et al., 2019)	indirect (Student sample, no explicit generational cohort comparison)	yes	yes
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	indirect (Examination of applicants at the aggregate level)	yes	yes
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	indirect (Examines employees without distinguishing between generational cohorts)	yes	primarily
(Köchling et al., 2023)	indirect (Examination of applicants in general)	yes	yes

Note:

An analysis of the thematic focus shows that, of the eight identified preliminary key articles, only three publications are suitable for a more in-depth examination (Köchling et al., 2023; Langer et al., 2019; Tursunbayeva et al., 2025). The remaining articles primarily serve to contextual knowledge, as they do not address detailed cohort-specific distinctions. This finding supports the assumption of a deficient literature base within this field of research. The three selected preliminary key articles serve as the basis for further protocol development. Although these preliminary key articles do not conduct explicit cohort analyses either, they address aspects relevant to the scoping review, such as the acceptance of technological applications in human resource management and selection processes. The five excluded articles also provide essential terminology and topic-specific insights that are incorporated into the design of the search strategy. The aim of this approach is to refine the search parameters and maximize the validity of the search results.

Table 4: PCC-Matrix for Preliminary Key Papers search terms

Preliminary Key Articles – Keywords/Abstracts	Number of search terms	Population (Generational Cohort)	Concept (Perception/TAM)	Context (Recruiting)
(Tambe et al., 2019) Employees, data analysis, human capital, human resource ethics, hiring, recruitment, information systems, decision-making tools	8	Employees	Data analysis, human resources ethics, information systems, Decision-making tools	Hiring, Recruitment, human capital
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025) AI, Digital data, Candidate, Recruitment, Perception, Organizational attractiveness, Literature review	7	Candidate	AI, Digital data, Perception	Recruitment, Organizational attractiveness
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020) People, Fairness, Discrimination, Perceived fairness, Ethics, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM, Literature review	7	People	Fairness, Perceived fairness, Discrimination, Ethics, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM	-
(Köchling et al., 2021) Groups, Fairness, Bias, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Recruitment, Asynchronous video interview, Ethics, HR analytics, Artificial intelligence	9	Groups	Artificial intelligence, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Fairness, Bias, Ethics	Recruitment, Asynchronous video interview
(Langer et al., 2019) People, applicant reactions, contextual influences, highly automated job interviews, human resource management, videoconference interviews	6	People	highly automated job interviews	applicant reactions, contextual influences, human resource management, videoconference interviews
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022) People, Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Employee selection, Ethical	7	People	Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Ethical recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI	Employee selection

recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI				
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023) Workers, Human resource management, Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Value creation, Job autonomy, Duality	7	Workers	Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Job autonomy, Duality	Human resource management, Value creation
(Köchling et al., 2023) Employees, Artificial intelligence, Opportunity to perform, Creepiness, Attractiveness, Applicant's acceptance, Recruitment	7	Employees	Artificial intelligence, Creepiness, Applicant's acceptance	Opportunity to perform, Attractiveness, Recruitment

Table 5: Predefined and Expanded Search Terms before Pilot Test

	Population (Generational Cohort)	Concept (Perception/TAM)	Context (Recruiting)
Expanding search terminology to enhance the quality of search results	Baby Boomer, Generation, Applicant, Age group, Age difference, Generational, Cohort, Digital Immigrants, Digital Native, Millennial	Semantic matching, Cut-off-threshold, TAM, Technology Acceptance Model, Machine learning, Natural Language Processing	CV Screening, CV-Screening, hiring funnel, screening process, Recruiting process, Resume screening
Usable search terms for the Pilot Test (Author Keywords and supplementary terms)	Candidate, Employees, People, Groups, Workers, Baby Boomer, Generation, Applicant, Age group, Age difference, Generational, Cohort, Digital Immigrants, Digital Native, Millennial, Cohort effect, Generational perspective, Generation gap	Data analysis, human resource ethics, information systems, Decision-making tools, decision making tool, AI, Digital data, Perception, Fairness, Perceived fairness, Discrimination, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Bias, Ethics, highly automated job interviews, Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Ethical recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI, Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Job autonomy, Duality, Creepiness, Applicant's acceptance, Semantic matching, Cut-off-threshold, TAM, Technology Acceptance Model, Machine learning, Natural Language Processing	Hiring, human capital, Recruitment, Organizational attractiveness, Asynchronous video interview, applicant reactions, contextual influences, human resource management, videoconference interviews, Employee selection, Opportunity to perform, Attractiveness, CV Screening, CV-Screening, Value creation, Hiring funnel, Screening process, Resume screening, personnel selection

Appendix 2

Table 6: Documentation of the first Pilot Test protocol

I	D	Db	Uss	T.a.	R.Q.*	P.Q.**	E
1	02/27/26	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("baby boomer" OR applicant OR candidate) AND ("artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "algorithmic hiring") AND (recruitment OR "human resource management" OR hiring))	6,530	100%	0%	The search results were excessively broad, leading to low precision. All identified preliminary key articles were retrieved. Crucial studies regarding generational cohort comparisons, semantic matching and cut-off threshold, were not captured. Furthermore, specific constructs such as perceptions and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) were not explicitly addressed.
2	03/09/26	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (applicant OR candidate OR "generational cohort") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "highly automated" OR "semantic matching") AND (recruitment OR "human resource management" OR "CV screening"))	5,268	100%	2%	The search results were excessively broad, resulting in low precision. All preliminary key articles were retrieved. Furthermore, the search failed to yield sufficient substantive literature explicitly addressing semantic matching and cut-off thresholds. Notably, generational cohort comparisons within the specific context of the screening process were underrepresented.
3	03/09/26	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (applicant OR candidate OR "generational cohort" OR "generational perspective") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "highly automated" OR "semantic matching" OR "cut-off threshold") AND (recruitment OR "human resource management" OR "CV screening" OR "resume screening"))	5,326	100%	0%	The search results were excessively broad, leading to low precision. While all preliminary key articles were successfully retrieved, the search failed to yield a sufficient number of substantive articles explicitly addressing semantic matching and cut-off thresholds. Notably research regarding generational cohort comparisons within the specific context of the screening stage remains underrepresented.
4	03/09/26	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (applicant OR candidate OR "generational cohort" OR	3,622	100%	2%	All preliminary key articles were retrieved. While the

		"generational perspective" OR "age group" OR "generation gap") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "highly automated" OR "semantic matching" OR "cut-off threshold" OR TAM OR "technology acceptance model" OR "decision-making tools") AND (recruitment OR "human resource management" OR "CV screening" OR "resume screening" OR "human capital" OR "personnel selection" OR hiring) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"COMP")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English"))			search yielded a high volume of literature on recruitment and resume screening, specific constructs (semantic matching, cut-off thresholds, TAM, and Generational Cohort Theory) were not in one context explicitly represented. The search was restricted to peer reviewed journal articles published in English within the subject areas of Computer science, Social Science, and Business, Management and Accounting. Furthermore, across all iterations, certain thematically relevant articles were excluded due insufficient journal rankings. Additionally, search terms associated with the subject matter were utilized (see Appendix 1: Table 5)
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Legend: I – Iteration / D – Date / Db – Database / Uss – Used searching string / T.a. – Total articles / R.Q. – Recall Quote / P.Q. – Precision Quote / E - Evaluation

*Formular: Recall Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of founded Preliminary Key Papers with search terms}}{\text{Total Preliminary Key papers (3)}} \times 100$

**Formular: Precision Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of relevant articles in the sample}}{\text{Total sample size (50)}} \times 100$

Note:

During the Pilot Test, truncation operators were deliberately not used. This was done to ensure terminological precision and the exact calibration of the search string. As part of the iterative Pilot Tests, the first fifty results, sorted by relevance, were reviewed in each instance to evaluate the recall and precision quotes. The use of truncation operators expanded the set of results what made it difficult to conduct a controlled evaluation of the relevance of individual search terms. For the actual scoping review, truncation operators are systematically applied to the defined search terms and within the databases used to maximize recall and ensure comprehensive coverage of the evidence.

Table 7: Pilot Extraction Matrix

<i>I</i>	<i>P. t. / J. t.</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>A. t.</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>M. K.</i>	<i>A. K.</i>	<i>E</i>
4	Article (IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management)	2024	16	From Bias to Brilliance: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Usage on Recruitment Biases in China	B	human resource management, Artificial intelligence, AI	Artificial intelligence (AI), human resource management, recruitment biases	Investigates the impact of AI implementation on biases within the recruitment process and to provide a critical evaluation of these effects in China.

Legend: I – Iteration / P. t. – Publication type / J. t. – Journal title / D – Date / C – Citations / A. t. - Article title / R - Rating (VHB-Rating) / M. K. – Matching Keywords / A. K. – Author Keywords / E - Evaluation

Table 8: Predefined and Expanded Search Terms after Pilot Test and with terms of the Pilot Extraction Matrix

	Population (Generational Cohort)	Concept (Perception/TAM)	Context (Recruiting)
Usable search terms for the Pilot Test (Author Keywords and supplementary terms)	Candidate, Employees, People, Groups, Workers, Baby Boomer, Generation, Applicant, Age group, Age difference, Generational, Cohort, Digital Immigrants, Digital Native, Millennial, Cohort effect, Generational perspective, Generation gap	Data analysis, human resource ethics, information systems, Decision-making tools, decision making tool, AI, Digital data, Perception, Fairness, Perceived fairness, Discrimination, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Bias, Ethics, highly automated job interviews, Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Ethical recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI, Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Job autonomy, Duality, Creepiness, Applicant’s acceptance, Semantic matching, Cut-off-threshold, TAM, Technology Acceptance Model, Machine learning, Natural Language Processing	Hiring, human capital, Recruitment, Organizational attractiveness, Asynchronous video interview, applicant reactions, contextual influences, human resource management, videoconference interviews, Employee selection, Opportunity to perform, Attractiveness, CV Screening, CV-Screening, Value creation, Hiring funnel, Screening process, Resume screening, personnel selection
Expanding search terminology to enhance the quality of search results	-	recruitment biases	-

Appendix 3

Table 9: Expansion of Table 2 Conceptual Search Matrix – Preliminary Key Articles

<i>A</i>	<i>A. t.</i>	<i>J. t.</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>ACI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A. E.</i>	<i>V. d.</i>
(Tambe et al., 2019)	Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources Management: Challenges and a Path Forward	California Management Review	B	96	The article is based on qualitative-empirical research involving workshops and surveys. It develops a rationale for the application of AI in Human resource management (HRM).	Examination of applicants and employees. Theoretical foundation for semantic matching and fairness considerations. Rationale for the screening stage.	02/11/26 - 2:52 pm
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	Artificial intelligence and digital data in recruitment. Exploring business and engineering candidates 'perceptions of organizational attractiveness	European Management Journal	B	5	Vignette based survey experiment / Experimental manipulation, N=265.	Provides data on the perceptions of generational cohorts entering the labor market. Examines technology acceptance and the evaluation of AI-driven decisions.	02/11/26 - 3:14 pm
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	Discriminated by an algorithm: a systematic review of discrimination and fairness by algorithmic decision-making in the context of HR recruitment and HR development	Business Research	B	360	Systematic Literature analysis / PRISMA guidelines / Article examined from 2014 to 2020.	Reports on fairness perceptions and the imperative to investigate them. Focuses on the CV screening process and algorithmic bias.	02/11/26 - 3:36 pm
(Köchling et al., 2021)	Highly Accurate, But Still Discriminatory	Business & Information Systems Engineering	B	73	Exploratory approach to criteria evaluation. Objective of the technical audit of algorithms with respect to their fairness.	While fairness is evaluated from a technical perspective, generational cohort-specific perceptions are not. Measuring algorithmic discrimination despite high accuracy, as well as assessing equal opportunity.	02/15/26 - 9:16 am
(Langer et al., 2019)	Highly automated job interviews: Acceptance under the	International Journal of Selection and Assessment	B	133	2x2 Between-Subjects-Design / N=123.	Identification of younger target groups regarding acceptance and the decline in	02/15/26 - 9:22 am

	influence of stakes					acceptance at high levels of automation.	
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	Ethics of AI-Enabled Recruiting and Selection: A Review and Research Agenda	Journal of Business Ethics	B	324	Systematic literature analysis employing an interpretive approach.	Examination of applicants and AI mechanisms. Classification of AI across the recruitment stages.	02/15/26 - 9:26 am
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	The duality of algorithmic management: Toward a research agenda on HRM algorithms, autonomy and value creation	Human Resource Management Review	A	162	Conceptual study grounded in structuration theory and the duality of technology framework.	Conceptual examination of employees. Abroad HRM framework with reference to CV screening and a theoretical foundation for algorithmic systems.	02/15/26 - 9:30 am
(Köchling et al., 2023)	Can I show my skills? Affective responses to artificial intelligence in the recruitment process	Review of Managerial Science	B	92	Scenario-based experiment using a Between-Subjects-Design / N=160.	It becomes evident that the generational cohort perspective remains largely unexplored. This study provides evidence on how the use of AI influences trust and fairness perceptions.	02/15/26 - 9:38 am
(Zheng et al., 2024)	From Bias to Brilliance: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Usage on Recruitment Biases in China	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	B	16	Cross-sectional dataset. N=432 respondents working in the manufacturing sector.	Examines both AI and the human factor, the latter of which remains indispensable the recruitment process. This approach facilitates a differentiated view on the role of AI in recruitment.	03/09/26 - 9:21 am

Legend: A – Author / A. t. – Article title / J. t. – Journal title / R – Rating (VHB-Rating 2024) / ACI – Article Citation Index / M – Methodology / A. E. – Article Evaluation / V. d. – Viewing date

Table 10: Expansion of Table 3 PCC-Fit - Preliminary Key Articles

Preliminary Key Articles	P (Generational Cohort)	C (Perception/TAM)	C (Recruiting)
(Tambe et al., 2019)	indirect (Examines applicants and employees)	yes	yes
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	indirect (Examines students and early-career professionals)	yes	yes
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	indirect (Examines groups of Race, Gender, Age)	yes	yes
(Köchling et al., 2021)	indirect (Examines the evaluation of fairness metrics for applicants)	yes	yes
(Langer et al., 2019)	indirect (Student sample, no explicit generational cohort comparison)	yes	yes
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	indirect (Examination of applicants at the aggregate level)	yes	yes
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	indirect (Examines employees without distinguishing between generational cohorts)	yes	primarily
(Köchling et al., 2023)	indirect (Examination of applicants in general)	yes	yes
(Zheng et al., 2024)	indirect (Examination of workers in the manufacturing sector)	yes	yes

Table 11: Expansion of Table 4 PCC-Matrix for Preliminary Key Papers search terms

Preliminary Key Articles – Keywords/Abstracts *	Number of search terms	Population (Generational Cohort)	Concept (Perception/TAM)	Context (Recruiting)
(Tambe et al., 2019) Employees, data analysis, human capital, human resource ethics, hiring, recruitment, information systems, decision-making tools	8	Employees	Data analysis, human resources ethics, information systems, Decision-making tools	Hiring, Recruitment, human capital
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025) AI, Digital data, Candidate, Recruitment, Perception, Organizational attractiveness, Literature review	7	Candidate	AI, Digital data, Perception	Recruitment, Organizational attractiveness
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020) People, Fairness, Discrimination, Perceived fairness, Ethics, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM, Literature review	7	People	Fairness, Perceived fairness, Discrimination, Ethics, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM	-
(Köchling et al., 2021) Groups, Fairness, Bias, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Recruitment, Asynchronous video interview, Ethics, HR analytics, Artificial intelligence	9	Groups	Artificial intelligence, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Fairness, Bias, Ethics	Recruitment, Asynchronous video interview
(Langer et al., 2019) People, applicant reactions, contextual influences, highly automated job interviews, human resource management, videoconference interviews	6	People	highly automated job interviews	applicant reactions, contextual influences, human resource management, videoconference interviews
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022) People, Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Employee selection, Ethical	7	People	Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Ethical recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI	Employee selection

recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI				
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023) Workers, Human resource management, Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Value creation, Job autonomy, Duality	7	Workers	Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Job autonomy, Duality	Human resource management
(Köchling et al., 2023) Employees, Artificial intelligence, Opportunity to perform, Creepiness, Attractiveness, Applicant's acceptance, Recruitment	7	Employees	Artificial intelligence, Creepiness, Applicant's acceptance	Opportunity to perform, Attractiveness, Recruitment
(Zheng et al., 2024) Artificial intelligence (AI), human resource management, recruitment biases	3, (4)	-	Artificial intelligence, (AI), recruitment biases	human resource management

*Not all newly identified keywords were incorporated, as they did not lead to a substantive improvement in the quality of the search results.

Appendix 4

Table 12: Keyword occurrence within the preliminary articles from the Pilot Extraction Matrix before

Preliminary Article	Used search terms*	Keyword occurrence
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025; Zheng et al., 2024)	AI	2
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	algorithmic decision-making in HRM	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	algorithmic hiring	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	algorithmic management	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	algorithms	1
(Langer et al., 2019)	applicant reactions	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	applicant's acceptance	1
(Köchling et al., 2021)	artificial algorithmic decision making	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022; Köchling et al., 2021, 2023; Zheng et al., 2024)	artificial intelligence	4
(Köchling et al., 2021)	asynchronous video interview	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	attractiveness	1
(Köchling et al., 2021)	bias	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	bias of ai	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	candidate	1
(Langer et al., 2019)	contextual influences	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	creepiness	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	data analysis	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	decision-making tools	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	digital data	1
((Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	discrimination	1
(Zheng et al., 2024)	recruitment biases	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	duality	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	employee selection	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	ethical recruitment	1
(Köchling et al., 2021; Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	ethics	2
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	ethics of ai	1
(Köchling et al., 2021; Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	fairness	2
(Langer et al., 2019)	highly automated job interviews	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	hiring	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	human capital	1
(Langer et al., 2019; Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023; Zheng et al., 2024)	human resource management	3
(Tambe et al., 2019)	human resources ethics	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	information systems	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	job autonomy	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	opportunity to perform	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	organizational attractiveness	1
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	perceived fairness	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	perception	1
(Köchling et al., 2021, 2023; Tambe et al., 2019; Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	recruitment	4
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	value creation	1
(Langer et al., 2019)	videoconference interviews	1

*Validating keyword relevance and search string effectiveness.

Table 13: Expansion of Search terms and Documentation of the second Pilot Test protocol

I	D	Db	Uss	T.a.	R.Q.*	P.Q.**	E
1	03/09/26	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (applicant OR candidate OR "generational cohort" OR "generational perspective" OR "age group" OR "generation gap") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "highly automated" OR "semantic matching" OR "cut-off threshold" OR TAM OR "technology acceptance model" OR "decision-making tools") AND (recruitment OR "human resource management" OR "CV screening" OR "resume screening" OR "human capital" OR "personnel selection" OR hiring OR "recruitment biases")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"COMP")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English")))	3,622	100%	4%	All preliminary key articles were retrieved. The search yielded a high volume of literature predominantly focused on recruitment and resume screening. Specific constructs such as semantic matching, cut-off thresholds, TAM and Generational Cohort Theory were not explicitly represented. The scope was restricted to peer reviewed journal articles published in English within the subject areas of Computer Science, Social Science, and Business, Management and Accounting. Additionally, search terms associated with the subject matter were utilized (see Appendix 2: Table 8)

Legend: I – Iteration / D – Date / Db – Database / Uss – Used searching string / T.a. – Total articles / R.Q. – Recall Quote / P.Q. – Precision Quote / E- Evaluation

*Formular: Recall Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of founded Preliminary Key Papers with search terms}}{\text{Total Preliminary Key papers (4)}} \times 100$

**Formular: Precision Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of relevant articles in the sample}}{\text{Total sample size (50)}} \times 100$

Table 14: Pilot Extraction Matrix

<i>I</i>	<i>P. t. / J. t.</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>A. t.</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>M. K.</i>	<i>A. K.</i>	<i>E</i>
1	Article (Human resource Management Journal)	2019	91	When your resume is (not) turning you down: Modelling ethnic bias in resume screening	A	resume screening, applicant, bias, resume- screening, discrimination	discrimination, diversity, ethnicity, recruitment, resume screening	It establishes the benchmark against which generational differences in the perception and acceptance of AI are evaluated.

Legend: I – Iteration / P. t. – Publication type / J. t. – Journal title / D – Date / C – Citations / A. t. - Article title / R - Rating (VHB-Rating) / M. K. – Matching Keywords / A. K. – Author Keywords / E - Evaluation

Table 15: Predefined and Expanded Search Terms after second Pilot Test and with terms of the Pilot Extraction Matrix

	Population (Generational Cohort)	Concept (Perception/TAM)	Context (Recruiting)
Usable search terms for the Pilot Test (Author Keywords and supplementary terms)	Candidate, Employees, People, Groups, Workers, Baby Boomer, Generation, Applicant, Age group, Age difference, Generational, Cohort, Digital Immigrants, Digital Native, Millennial, Cohort effect, Generational perspective, Generation gap	Data analysis, human resource ethics, information systems, Decision-making tools, decision making tool, AI, Digital data, Perception, Fairness, Perceived fairness, Discrimination, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Bias, Ethics, highly automated job interviews, Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Ethical recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI, Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Job autonomy, Duality, Creepiness, Applicant’s acceptance, Semantic matching, Cut-off-threshold, TAM, Technology Acceptance Model, Machine learning, Natural Language Processing, recruitment biases	Hiring, human capital, Recruitment, Organizational attractiveness, Asynchronous video interview, applicant reactions, contextual influences, human resource management, videoconference interviews, Employee selection, Opportunity to perform, Attractiveness, CV Screening, CV-Screening, Value creation, Hiring funnel, Screening process, Resume screening, personnel selection
Expanding search terminology to enhance the quality of search results	-	-	-

Table 16: Expansion of Table 9 Conceptual Search Matrix – Preliminary Key Articles

<i>A</i>	<i>A. t.</i>	<i>J. t.</i>	<i>R.</i>	<i>ACI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A. E.</i>	<i>V. d.</i>
(Tambe et al., 2019)	Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources Management: Challenges and a Path Forward	California Management Review	B	96	The article is based on qualitative-empirical research involving workshops and surveys. It develops a rationale for the application of AI in Human resource management (HRM).	Examination of applicants and employees. Theoretical foundation for semantic matching and fairness considerations. Rationale for the screening stage.	02/11/26 - 2:52 pm
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	Artificial intelligence and digital data in recruitment. Exploring business and engineering candidates 'perceptions of organizational attractiveness	European Management Journal	B	5	Vignette based survey experiment / Experimental manipulation, N=265.	Provides data on the perceptions of generational cohorts entering the labor market. Examines technology acceptance and the evaluation of AI-driven decisions.	02/11/26 - 3:14 pm
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	Discriminated by an algorithm: a systematic review of discrimination and fairness by algorithmic decision-making in the context of HR recruitment and HR development	Business Research	B	360	Systematic Literature analysis / PRISMA guidelines / Article examined from 2014 to 2020.	Reports on fairness perceptions and the imperative to investigate them. Focuses on the CV screening process and algorithmic bias.	02/11/26 - 3:36 pm
(Köchling et al., 2021)	Highly Accurate, But Still Discriminatory	Business & Information Systems Engineering	B	73	Exploratory approach to criteria evaluation. Objective of the technical audit of algorithms with respect to their fairness.	While fairness is evaluated from a technical perspective, generational cohort-specific perceptions are not. Measuring algorithmic discrimination despite high accuracy, as well as assessing equal opportunity.	02/15/26 - 9:16 am
(Langer et al., 2019)	Highly automated job interviews: Acceptance under the	International Journal of Selection and Assessment	B	133	2x2 Between-Subjects-Design / N=123.	Identification of younger target groups regarding acceptance and the decline in acceptance at high levels of automation.	02/15/26 - 9:22 am

	influence of stakes						
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	Ethics of AI-Enabled Recruiting and Selection: A Review and Research Agenda	Journal of Business Ethics	B	324	Systematic literature analysis employing an interpretive approach.	Examination of applicants and AI mechanisms. Classification of AI across the recruitment stages.	02/15/26 - 9:26 am
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	The duality of algorithmic management: Toward a research agenda on HRM algorithms, autonomy and value creation	Human Resource Management Review	A	162	Conceptual study grounded in structuration theory and the duality of technology framework.	Conceptual examination of employees. Abroad HRM framework with reference to CV screening and a theoretical foundation for algorithmic systems.	02/15/26 - 9:30 am
(Köchling et al., 2023)	Can I show my skills? Affective responses to artificial intelligence in the recruitment process	Review of Managerial Science	B	92	Scenario-based experiment using a Between-Subjects-Design / N=160.	It becomes evident that the generational cohort perspective remains largely unexplored. This study provides evidence on how the use of AI influences trust and fairness perceptions.	02/15/26 - 9:38 am
(Zheng et al., 2024)	From Bias to Brilliance: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Usage on Recruitment Biases in China	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	B	16	Cross-sectional dataset. N=432 respondents working in the manufacturing sector.	Examines both AI and the human factor, the latter of which remains indispensable the recruitment process. This approach facilitates a differentiated view on the role of AI in recruitment.	03/09/26 - 9:21 am
(Derous & Ryan, 2019)	When your resume is (not) turning you down: Modelling ethnic bias in resume screening	Human Resource Management Journal	A	91	Three-stage model of biased resume screening. Intervention analysis.	Findings regarding applicants' perceptions of bias during the screening stage contribute to an understanding of the emergence of bias, particularly within the context of AI-supported resume screening.	03/09/26 - 11:42 am

Legend: A – Author / A. t. – Article title / J. t. – Journal title / R – Rating (VHB-Rating 2024) / ACI – Article Citation Index / M – Methodology / A. E. – Article Evaluation / V. d. – Viewing date

Table 17: Expansion of Table 10 PCC-Fit - Preliminary Key Articles

Preliminary Key Articles	P (Generational Cohort)	C (Perception/TAM)	C (Recruiting)
(Tambe et al., 2019)	indirect (Examines applicants and employees)	yes	yes
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	indirect (Examines students and early-career professionals)	yes	yes
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	indirect (Examines groups of Race, Gender, Age)	yes	yes
(Köchling et al., 2021)	indirect (Examines the evaluation of fairness metrics for applicants)	yes	yes
(Langer et al., 2019)	indirect (Student sample, no explicit generational cohort comparison)	yes	yes
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	indirect (Examination of applicants at the aggregate level)	yes	yes
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	indirect (Examines employees without distinguishing between generational cohorts)	yes	primarily
(Köchling et al., 2023)	indirect (Examination of applicants in general)	yes	yes
(Zheng et al., 2024)	indirect (Examination of workers in the manufacturing sector)	yes	yes
(Deros & Ryan, 2019)	indirect (Examination of applicants while the resume-screening stage)	yes	yes

Table 18: Expansion of Table 11 PCC-Matrix for Preliminary Key Papers search terms

Preliminary Key Articles – Keywords/Abstracts *	Number of search terms	Population (Generational Cohort)	Concept (Perception/TAM)	Context (Recruiting)
(Tambe et al., 2019) Employees, data analysis, human capital, human resource ethics, hiring, recruitment, information systems, decision-making tools	8	Employees	Data analysis, human resources ethics, information systems, Decision-making tools	Hiring, Recruitment, human capital
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025) AI, Digital data, Candidate, Recruitment, Perception, Organizational attractiveness, Literature review	7	Candidate	AI, Digital data, Perception	Recruitment, Organizational attractiveness
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020) People, Fairness, Discrimination, Perceived fairness, Ethics, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM, Literature review	7	People	Fairness, Perceived fairness, Discrimination, Ethics, Algorithmic decision-making in HRM	-
(Köchling et al., 2021) Groups, Fairness, Bias, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Recruitment, Asynchronous video interview, Ethics, HR analytics, Artificial intelligence	9	Groups	Artificial intelligence, Artificial algorithmic decision making, Fairness, Bias, Ethics	Recruitment, Asynchronous video interview
(Langer et al., 2019) People, applicant reactions, contextual influences, highly automated job interviews, human resource management, videoconference interviews	6	People	highly automated job interviews	applicant reactions, contextual influences, human resource management, videoconference interviews
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022) People, Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Employee selection, Ethical	7	People	Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic hiring, Ethical recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI	Employee selection

recruitment, Ethics of AI, Bias of AI				
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023) Workers, Human resource management, Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Value creation, Job autonomy, Duality	7	Workers	Algorithms, Algorithmic management, Job autonomy, Duality	Human resource management
(Köchling et al., 2023) Employees, Artificial intelligence, Opportunity to perform, Creepiness, Attractiveness, Applicant's acceptance, Recruitment	7	Employees	Artificial intelligence, Creepiness, Applicant's acceptance	Opportunity to perform, Attractiveness, Recruitment
(Zheng et al., 2024) Artificial intelligence (AI), human resource management, recruitment biases	3, (4)	-	Artificial intelligence, (AI), recruitment biases	human resource management
(Deros & Ryan, 2019) discrimination, diversity, ethnicity, recruitment, resume screening	5	-	discrimination, diversity, ethnicity	recruitment, resume screening

*Not all newly identified keywords were incorporated, as they did not lead to a substantive improvement in the quality of the search results.

Table 19: Keyword occurrence within the articles from the Pilot Extraction Matrix before

Preliminary Article	Used search terms*	Keyword occurrence
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025; Zheng et al., 2024)	AI	2
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	algorithmic decision-making in HRM	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	algorithmic hiring	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	algorithmic management	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	algorithms	1
(Langer et al., 2019)	applicant reactions	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	applicant's acceptance	1
(Köchling et al., 2021)	artificial algorithmic decision making	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022; Köchling et al., 2021, 2023; Zheng et al., 2024)	artificial intelligence	4
(Köchling et al., 2021)	asynchronous video interview	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	attractiveness	1
(Köchling et al., 2021)	bias	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	bias of ai	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	candidate	1
(Langer et al., 2019)	contextual influences	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	creepiness	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	data analysis	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	decision-making tools	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	digital data	1
(Deros & Ryan, 2019; Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	discrimination	2
(Zheng et al., 2024)	recruitment biases	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	duality	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	employee selection	1
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	ethical recruitment	1
(Köchling et al., 2021; Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	ethics	2
(Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022)	ethics of ai	1
(Köchling et al., 2021; Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	fairness	2
(Langer et al., 2019)	highly automated job interviews	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	hiring	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	human capital	1
(Langer et al., 2019; Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023; Zheng et al., 2024)	human resource management	3
(Tambe et al., 2019)	human resources ethics	1
(Tambe et al., 2019)	information systems	1
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	job autonomy	1
(Köchling et al., 2023)	opportunity to perform	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	organizational attractiveness	1
(Köchling & Wehner, 2020)	perceived fairness	1
(Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	perception	1
(Deros & Ryan, 2019; Köchling et al., 2021, 2023; Tambe et al., 2019; Tursunbayeva et al., 2025)	recruitment	5
(Meijerink & Bondarouk, 2023)	value creation	1
(Langer et al., 2019)	videoconference interviews	1
(Deros & Ryan, 2019)	diversity	1
(Deros & Ryan, 2019)	ethnicity	1
(Deros & Ryan, 2019)	resume screening	1

*Validating keyword relevance and search string effectiveness.

Table 20: Expansion of Search terms and Documentation of the third Pilot Test protocol

I	D	Db	Uss	T.a.	R.Q.*	P.Q.**	E
1	03/09/26	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (applicant OR candidate OR "generational cohort" OR "generational perspective" OR "age group" OR "generation gap" OR "baby boomer" OR "Generation X" OR millennial OR "Generation Z" OR " Gen Z" OR "digital native") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "highly automated" OR "semantic matching" OR "cut-off threshold" OR TAM OR "technology acceptance model" OR "decision-making tools" OR "recruitment ethnicity") AND (recruitment OR "human resource management" OR "CV screening" OR "resume screening" OR "human capital" OR "personnel selection" OR hiring OR "recruitment biases")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"COMP") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BUSI"))	3,924	100%	6%	The number of results has increased. The recall and precision quotes remain the Additionally, search terms associated with the subject matter were utilized (see Appendix 4: Table 15)

Legend: I – Iteration / D – Date / Db – Database / Uss – Used searching string / T.a. – Total articles / R.Q. – Recall Quote / P.Q. – Precision Quote / E- Evaluation

*Formular: Recall Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of founded Preliminary Key Papers with search terms}}{\text{Total Preliminary Key papers (5)}} \times 100$

**Formular: Precision Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of relevant articles in the sample}}{\text{Total sample size (50)}} \times 100$

Appendix 5

Table 21: PRESS checklist on PCC framework at the protocol on the preliminary key articles

Subjects	Questions	Extension	Explanation
Translation of the research question	Does the search strategy match the research question/PICO?	Does the search strategy match the research question/PCC-framework?	yes.
	Are the search concepts clear?	-	yes.
	Are there too many or too few PICO elements included?	Are all PCC elements (Population, Concept, Context) included?	yes.
	Are the search concepts too narrow or too broad?	-	Four iterations were conducted during the first pilot phase, followed by a subsequent iteration in the second and third pilot phase stage to define the research scope.
	Does the search retrieve too many or too few records? (Please show number of hits per line.)	-	The fourth iteration of the first Pilot Test retrieved 3,622 articles (03/09/26 – Appendix 2: Table 6). The second Pilot Test (03/09/26 – Appendix 4: Table 13) yielded 3,622 articles, thereby constituting a representative and valid amount of relevant literature.
	Are unconventional or complex strategies explained?	-	No unconventional approaches or strategies were employed.
Boolean and proximity operators	Are Boolean or proximity operators used correctly?	-	yes, depending on the specific database logic.
	Is the use of nesting with brackets appropriate and effective for the search?	-	yes.
	If NOT is used, is this likely to result in any unintended exclusions?	-	NOT isn't used.
	Could precision be improved by using proximity operators (eg, adjacent, near, within) or phrase searching instead of AND?	-	no.
	Is the width of proximity operators suitable (eg, might adj5 pick up more variants than adj2)?	-	yes.
Subject headings	Are the subject headings relevant?	-	yes.
	Are any relevant subject headings missing; for example, previous index terms?	-	yes, e.g., by utilizing “data analysis” or “machine learning” instead of the broader term “artificial intelligence”.
	Are any subject headings too broad or too narrow?	-	no.

	Are subject headings exploded where necessary and vice versa?	-	no, to prevent a rigid framework of broader and narrower terms from distorting the retrieval outcomes.
	Are major headings (“starring” or restrict to focus) used? If so, is there adequate justification?	-	Major headings are used, but they are not with a restrict focus.
	Are subheadings missing?	-	no.
	Are subheadings attached to subject headings? (Floating subheadings may be preferred.)	-	yes.
	Are floating subheadings relevant and used appropriately?	-	yes.
	Are both subject headings and terms in free text (see the following) used for each concept?	-	yes (see Appendix 2, 4, 6: Table 6, 13, 20, 22).
Text word searching	Does the search include all spelling variants in free text (eg, UK vs. US spelling)?	-	No specific spelling constraints were imposed. All relevant search terms were verified. The number of retrieved articles remained constant, and the precision quote was unaffected. Truncations and wildcards will be used in the final scoping review
	Does the search include all synonyms or antonyms (eg, opposites)?	-	yes, e.g., CV screening, resume screening.
	Does the search capture relevant truncation (ie, is truncation at the correct place)?	-	not used.
	Is the truncation too broad or too narrow?	-	not used.
	Are acronyms or abbreviations used appropriately?	-	yes.
	Do they capture irrelevant material?	-	yes. During the Pilot Tests. No further relevant findings occurred in iterations three and four and the other Pilot Tests.
	Are the full terms also included?	-	yes.
	Are the keywords specific enough or too broad?	-	yes, e.g., Semantic matching, cut-off threshold, Technology Acceptance Model.
	Are too many or too few keywords used?	-	There are six keywords in use.
	Are stop words used?	-	yes – e.g., “decision-making tools”.
	Have the appropriate fields been searched; for example, is the choice of the text word fields (.tw.) or all fields (.af.)	-	The Scopus database was utilized for pilot testing, with the search restricted to the database-specific TITLE-ABS-KEY field to enhance precision and

	appropriate?		minimize irrelevant results.
	Are there any other fields to be included or excluded (database specific)?		no.
	Should any long strings be broken into several shorter search statements?	-	no.
Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	Are there any spelling errors?	-	no.
	Are there any errors in system syntax; for example, the use of a truncation symbol from a different search interface?	-	no.
	Are there incorrect line combinations or orphan lines (ie, lines that are not referred to in the final summation that could indicate an error in an AND or OR statement)?	-	no.
Limits and filters	Are all limits and filters used appropriately and are they relevant given the research question?	-	yes.
	Are all limits and filters used appropriately and are they relevant for the database?	-	yes.
	Are any potentially helpful limits or filters missing?	-	Limits with language, subject area, and document type.
	Are the limits or filters too broad or too narrow?	-	no.
	Can any limits or filters be added or taken away?	-	yes, but the found articles would increase
	Are sources cited for the filters used?	-	The study follows the PRISMA-ScR and the JBI-Guidelines (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Tricco et al., 2018)

To objectively ensure technical validity, the search strategy for the protocol was subjected to an expert review by an information specialist from the university (HTWG Konstanz). The evaluation focused on the precise application of database-specific syntax (Scopus) and logical integration of the PCC framework. The institution does not provide a formalized certification process for search strategies, validation was performed informally through a professional assessment aligned with the PRESS checklist. The resulting feedback was iteratively incorporated into the final search string.

Appendix 6:

Figure 1: PRISMA flowchart of search outcome and screening - template:

Figure 1: In accordance with (Tricco et al., 2018)

Legend of the PRISMA flow diagram template - colored elements: Blue – Name of the database / Purple – PRISMA flow stage / Black – Explanation of inclusion and exclusion criteria / Orange – Number of excluded articles / Green – Articles for the final exclusion

Table 22: Final examination of peer-reviewed articles in the protocol

I	D	Db	Uss	T.a.	R.Q.*	P.Q.**	E
1	04/01/26	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (applicant OR candidate OR "generational cohort" OR "generational perspective" OR "age group" OR "generation gap" OR "baby boomer" OR "Generation X" OR millennial OR "Generation Z" OR " Gen Z" OR "digital native") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "highly automated" OR "semantic matching" OR "cut-off threshold" OR TAM OR "technology acceptance model" OR "decision-making tools" OR "recruitment ethnicity") AND (recruitment OR "human resource management" OR "CV screening" OR "resume screening" OR "human capital" OR "personnel selection" OR hiring OR "recruitment biases")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"COMP") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BUSI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English"))	3,924	100%	6%	No increase in the number of search results compared to the third Pilot Test. No additional sources relevant to the topic could be identified.

Legend: I – Iteration / D – Date / Db – Database / Uss – Used searching string / T.a. – Total articles / R.Q. – Recall Quote / P.Q. – Precision Quote / E- Evaluation

*Formular: Recall Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of founded Preliminary Key Papers with search terms}}{\text{Total Preliminary Key papers (5)}} \times 100$

**Formular: Precision Quote = $\frac{\text{Number of relevant articles in the sample}}{\text{Total sample size (50)}} \times 100$